

TITLE: ANALYSIS OF THE MISCONCEPTIONS OF ECO-THEOLOGY HELD ON BY BASIC SCHOOL STUDENTS AND TEACHERS IN GHANA

ABSTRACT

The issues of climate change and global warming have been accompanied by various non-empirical researches that have opposing views on whether religion could promote environmental education. Therefore, this empirical study used experimental survey to analyse the misconceptions of eco-theology held on by basic school students and teachers in a diverse community, Obuasi.

54.05% of responses from all students while 36.92% of responses from all teachers at two schools revealed misconceptions held on Eco-Theology. The vast majority of the participants engaged in regular religious and/ or environmental activities in contrast to other literatures. These two factors could serve as pivots for further eco-theology education. The concepts of “We reap what we sow” endorsing environmental stewardship and accountability could be engaged in tutelage to correct these misconceptions. However, the roles of God and man in environmental protection must be clarified as the religious education syllabi for schools in Ghana could not.

KEYWORDS

Ecotheology, Environment, Religion, Misconceptions, Students, Education

INTRODUCTION

One of the emerging alternatives to environmental protection is Eco-theology, a subcategory of science and religion, the hoary adversaries. According to Conradie, Bergmann, Deane-Drummond & Edwards (2014), religions should be flexible, amenable to new perceptions and able to forgo unfeasible beliefs, interpretations and dogmas. Students sometimes yield to doctrinal misconceptions of right and wrong and need better “opportunities to interact and internalize the scriptural text” (Webb, 2007). Scientific conceptions oppose these naive thoughts dubbed misconceptions (Osborne & Wittrock, 1985). Scholars and tutors have revealed that naive notions about natural occurrences are held on to by students even after they have been educated on these misconceptions.

Even the adversaries of the role of religion as the underpinnings of morality and the indicators of religion as the source of our conservation distresses have projected that the elucidation to the conservational crisis should embrace the utility of religion. The RE Council (REC) of UK which opposed that religion was the underpinning of morality also believed that the “concern for nature was essential to religion and that religious awareness had vital contribution to make in encouraging a respect for nature” (Religions and Environmental Education Programme (REEP), 1994, Hammelt, 2012,70). White still advocated that “human ecology is deeply conditioned by beliefs about our nature and destiny—that is, by religion” (White, 1967, 1204). White had commented that Christianity was a reason for our ecological desolations. Therefore, instead of religion encouraging ecological complications, religion can be used to resolve ecological problems. Our beliefs can be moulded by Religious Education (R.E). Therefore, White suggested that “Human ecology is deeply conditioned by beliefs about our nature and destiny—that is, by religion” (White, 1967, 1204). Then, R.E can profile the philosophies about human ecology, nature and ecological conservation.

Ghana seems be a religious country. According to Ghana's 2010 Population and Housing census, a major 71.2% of the population is Christians, Islam has 17.6%, and only slight proportions of the population either observe the traditional religion (5.2%) or are not associated to any religion (5.3%). However, a foremost player in ethical or morality concerns in Africa is religion (Opoku, 1978). However, there are very few pivoting empirical works done on using religious education as a means for environmental education in Ghana.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

According to Asare (2022d), the religious education syllabi for grade 1-12 from elementary school to senior high school comprised of simply recognizable concepts of environmental education. Conversely, the religious education syllabi were deprived of illumination of the distinction between the role of God and the role of man in environmental protection. Awuah-Nyamekye (2019) reported that obstructions to eco-theology education in Ghana are nebulous ecological orientation of textbooks and absence of experienced instructors. Therefore, the teaching contents and methods of eco-theology based on the syllabus may fail to address misconceptions held on by students and teachers. Misconceptions obstruct concept learning. Therefore, misconceptions of eco-theology identified and addressed.

Various researches blame religion misconceptions as the cause of environmental problems and others have suggested that religion cannot be used to promote environmental education. However, not many have provided empirical evidence to back these claims especially among basic school students and teachers and in Ghana. Therefore, this study conducted an experimental survey to analyze the misconceptions of eco-theology held on by basic school students and teachers in a diverse community at Obuasi, Ghana.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a. To identify the types of misconceptions of Eco-Theology held on by the students and teachers.
- b. To analyze the differences in the types of misconceptions of Eco-Theology held on by the students and staff of the two different schools.
- c. To suggest solutions to rectify these misconceptions.

THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND THE RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Research Question 1: What percentages of all responses from the students and teachers in the schools indicate a type of misconception of eco-theology?

Research Question 2: What are the differences in the percentages of all responses from the students and teachers in the different schools that indicate a type of misconception related to Eco-Theology?

Hypotheses

- a. **Null hypotheses:** The sample means of the percentage of all the responses from students and teachers in the different schools revealing a type of misconception on Eco-Theology do not differ significantly.

b. **Alternate hypotheses:** The sample means of the percentage of all the responses students and teachers in the different schools revealing a type of misconception on Eco-Theology differ significantly.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will serve as the foundation for future descriptive studies on the nature of conceptions and the solutions to create conceptual change in Eco-theology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Asare (2022a), the religious education prospectuses for grade 1-12 from elementary school to senior high school contain easily identifiable concepts of environmental education. The curricula sought to shape in students characters care for the environment, sought to teach eco-spirituality conditioning ecological beliefs about nature destiny, teach subject specific practices about morals, character and attitude as well as tutor personal and social values that are essential for individual and societal growth and development. However, the difference between the role of man and the role of God is unresolved. The findings of Altmeyer (2021) revealed that environmental education was less feasible through religious education for the 14- to 16-year-old students at secondary schools in Germany and Austria. However, majority of the students Altmeyer (2021) reached engaged less in religious activities.

The Types of Misconceptions

Misconceptions in eco-theology include the Dominion misconception (Gottlieb, 2009); Fatalism misconception (Shehu, 2015); Divine Intervention misconception (Hope & Jones, 2014); Afterlife misconception (Hope & Jones, 2014); Divine Apocalypse misconception (Shehu, 2015); and Spirituality misconception (Shehu, 2015).

Dominion misconception is the misbelief that according to the Holy Bible and The Holy Quran, God has given humans the power to overexploit the environment. Therefore, humans have the power to carelessly exploit all other creatures in the environment. However, God gave humans the mandate to dress and to keep the Garden of Eden (Genesis 2:15).

Shehu (2015) studied the religious effects on both environmental distress and perceptions and behaviour and approaches of adaptation to environmental degradation in Northeast Nigeria. Shehu (2015) used significant dialogues that construe environmental change from an only theological perspective of the Divine Apocalypse misconception, where environmental change was framed either as God's way of punishing humanity's wrong deeds or as a fulfilment of the 'end times' prophesies (Shehu, 2015). Some people maintained that the cause of ecological problems as supernatural forces. Some participants dissociated humans from being the causal agents of environmental problems with the result that inaction was inevitable. Fatalism misconception, a theological knowledge of conceiving ecological problems as predicated on the belief in 'predestination' or 'fate' arises. Therefore there is the need for divine-intervention giving rise to the Divine-Intervention Misconception in Eco-theology. However, humans still have a special responsibility to minimize their impacts.

Afterlife misconception is the belief that the corrupt and imperfect natural world results in death as the cause of ecological problems (Hope & Jones, 2014; and Conradie, et. al, 2014). Hope & Jones (2014) studied the conceptions about climate change and Climate Capture Storage (CCS) technologies. Although Hope & Jones (2014), reported that Muslim and Christian conceptions about climate change and Climate Capture Storage (CCS) technologies were formed by the significance of intergenerational justice and environmental stewardship, both sets had relatively low perceptions for the resolve of environmental issues,

mainly climate change, because of their beliefs in divine interference and a life after death. CCS was not less challenging for Christians, who proved anthropocentric values and assessed environmental issues and technological solutions kin to the degree to which they sustained human well-being. Spirituality misconception is the belief that the solutions to ecological problems are only engaging in religious piety, forsaking materialism, rituals, repentance and charity (Shehu, 2015).

Calvin DeWitt (2000) contends, the Bible contains delightfully motivated wisdom about creation, and if we pay attention to this text, we can study to communicate to other creatures as God intends' (DeWitt (2000, as cited in Baumann et al., 2011, 59).

METHODOLOGY

Background of The Study

The world is faced with the issues of climate change and global warming and Ghana is no different to these effects. The study took place at two schools located at Gausu, an urban poor suburb that is a flood plain faced with regular floods for years in the Obuasi Municipal of the Ashanti Region of Ghana. The schools were chosen because the suburb had a huge population with diverse religion and culture.

Subjects

All 113 students who took part in the survey were basic school students from level 1-9 (elementary to middle school level). 76.11 % of all the students who answered the questionnaires were Christians while the rest were Muslims. Majority 66 students representing 58.41% of all the students were females and the rest were males. Also, only all the 13 teachers who taught Religious and Moral Education only or and other subjects at the related level 1-9 classes were surveyed. 88.50% of all students and all 13 teachers regularly engaged in religious activities such as private or congregational acts such as worship, prayer, drama, recitals, music and dance.

Experimental Design

One main session for the survey was used. This was preceded by a mini try test for ten (10) students in one of the schools to assess how the students understood the tests. During the main survey, the students were guided through the statements by reading out the statements and translating them in the local language with the help of the teachers and the researcher especially students below middle school level. Further clarifications of the ten (10) statements were allowed to be requested by the students and teachers. All fifty (50) students present at School 1 took part in the survey because of the low population of the school. However, only 63 students were selected at random to take part in the survey because of the high population of School 2.

In order to verify the frequency of participant's religious activities, all fifty (50) students at School 1 were interviewed to demonstrate a religious activity they often or recently did. However, all the teachers from both schools and all students from School 2 were asked to respond to the frequency and type of religious activity using the survey paper. The participants were assessed with ten (10) Statements of only three possible multiple-choice options (Yes, No and Untold) not more than what their syllabi and academic levels demanded.

Delimitations

Consent was sought from the school's authorities in order to allocate ample time for the tests. Caution was taken to avoid strict claims on the acts of God in ecological,

evolutionary and human history to avoid God’s perfection being compromised which could arouse conflict between science and religious concepts (Conradie, et. al, 2014).

Data Analysis Of The Work:

The occurrence of misconceptions were surveyed qualitatively but analyzed quantitatively. A t Test using Microsoft Excel was used to analyse the differences in the observed sample percentage means of the number of all students and teachers having or not having a type of misconception related to Eco-Theology.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Table 1.0. The Results For The Responses All Question/Statement In Eco-Theology.

QUESTION/ STATEMENT	Percentage of Responses Revealing A Type in Misconception				TYPE OF MISCONCEPTION	COMMENT
	SCHOOL 1	SCHOOL 2	BOTH SCHOOLS	ALL TEACHERS		
1. We get all the things we need from God	80%	81%	80.53%	53.85%	Dominion	Problem
3. God created us humans to take and use whatever we like from the environment	70%	76.2%	73.45%	61.54%	Dominion	Problem
6. Humans are the only creatures that need the environment.	56%	15.9%	33.63%	7.69%	Dominion	Can help Eco-Theology Education
9. Humans the only important creatures God made.	48%	33.3%	39.19%	7.69%	Dominion	Can help Eco-Theology Education
2. Humans cannot harm the environment, God protects all.	54%	33.3%	42.48%	53.85%	Divine Intervention	Can help Eco-Theology Education
5. You must use your talent to destroy the environment	36%	46%	41.59%	23.08%	Divine Intervention	Can help Eco-Theology Education

7. God is the only one who can change processes in nature like temperature, rainfall and sunshine.	94%	88.9%	91.15%	84.62%	Divine Intervention	Problem
4. God is the only one who can destroy the environment.	66%	61.9%	63.72%	61.54%	Divine Apocalypse	Problem
8. The scriptures teach us to only care about what happens after we die	64%	20.6%	39.82%	7.69%	Afterlife	Can help Eco-Theology Education
10. Religion can help us to protect the environment.	28%	27%	27.43%	7.69%	Eco-Theology	Can help Eco-Theology Education

Results for the Dominion Misconception

Majority 57.54% of all responses from the students from both schools revealed the Dominion misconception while minority 41.03% of all teachers from both schools revealed the Dominion misconception. Data Analyses using t-Test revealed that the observed percentage means of all students in School 1 and School 2 that disagreed to the dominion concept differed significantly based on four statements related to eco-theology. The responds to Statement 1 revealed that majority 80.53% of all the students and majority 53.85% of all the teachers from both schools agreed that they could get everything they needed from God. This idea formed the foundation of the dominion misconception. The responds to the Statement 3 also revealed that 73.45% of all the students and 61.54% of the teachers from both schools conceived that they could take whatever they wanted from the environment. There was a huge difference in the responses to the Statement 6 between the schools. While 56% of students at School 1 agreed to Statement 6 that humans are the only creatures that need the environment, 15.9% of students at School 2 also agreed. For Statement 6, minority 33.7% of all students and 7.69% of all teachers from both schools conceived that humans are the only creatures that need the environment. For Statement 9, majority 48% and 33.3% of all students in School 1 and School 2 respectively conceived that humans the only important creatures God made. Averagely, 39.82% of all students and 7.69% of all teachers from both schools agreed to Statement 9.

A t-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances revealed that the observed sample percentage means of 63.5% and 51.59% of all the response from students in School 1 and School 2 respectively represented to the dominion misconception based on Survey Statements 1, 3, 6 and 9. The t-test revealed that the sample means were convincing enough to say that the number of students from the two schools that had the dominion misconception differed significantly.

Results for the Divine Intervention Misconception

Averagely, majority 53.87 % of responses from all the students close to the majority 53.85 % of all the teachers from both schools had the Divine Intervention misconception. The

detailed results are as follow. All 113 students from both schools perceived the Divine Intervention related to statements 2, 5 and 7. A t-Test revealed that the observed percentage means of all students in School 1 (61.33%) and in School 2 (56.41%) that agreed to the Divine Intervention concept differed significantly based on the three statements. 42.48% of all students and 53.85% of all teachers from both schools agreed that humans could not harm the environment because God protects all (Statement 2). Majority 91.15 % of all students and 84.61% of all teachers from both schools supported that God is the only one who can change processes in nature like temperature, rainfall and sunshine (Statement 7). Therefore, this could be interpreted that a very huge majority of all the students and all teachers disagreed to the anthropogenic causes of climate change. Also, 41.59% of all students in contrast to 76.92% of all teachers from both schools disagreed that they could use their talents to act and protect the environment (Statement 5).

Results for the Divine Apocalypse Misconception

For the Divine Apocalypse Misconception related to Statement 4, only 66% and 61.9% of all the students in School 1 and School 2 respectively perceived that God is the only one who can destroy the environment. Averagely, 63.72% of all students and 61.54% of all teachers from both schools had the Divine Apocalypse Misconceptions related to Statement 4.

Results for the Afterlife Misconception

In response to Statement 8, averagely, 39.82% of all 113 students and majority 7.69% of all teachers from both schools had the Afterlife Misconception that the scriptures teach only about afterlife. However 64% of students in contrast to 20.6% of students from Schools 1 and 2 respectively had the Afterlife Misconception.

Results for the Concept of Eco-Theology

For the Concept of Eco-Theology related to Statement 10, the percentages of 72% and 73% of all the students in School 1 and School 2 respectively agreed that Religion could help us to protect the environment. Averagely, 72.57% of all students and 92.31% of all thirteen (13) teachers from both schools also agreed.

Results for the Differences in Misconceptions

A t-Test revealed from the responds that the observed sample percentage comparing the misconceptions of the teachers to the students differed significantly. Averagely, the majority 54.05% of all 113 students but the minority 36.92% of all teachers from both schools had misconceptions related to Eco-Theology.

A t-Test revealed from the responds of all 113 students to the ten (10) survey statements that the t Stat was less than the t Critical at two-tail so the null Hypotheses was rejected. The observed sample percentage means of the number of all students without misconceptions were 40.4% (at School 1) and 51.5% (at School 2). This was convincing enough to reveal that the differences in the percentage of students who had misconceptions on Eco-Theology between the two schools differed significantly.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Averagely, the majority 54.05% of responds from all 113 students but the minority 36.92% of all teachers from both schools indicated misconceptions related to Eco-Theology. These empirical findings relate to Asare's (2022d) findings on the probability of

misconceptions because the religious education syllabi were deprived of illumination of the distinction between the role of God and the role of man in environmental protection. Also, the results relate to Awuah-Nyamekye's (2019) research that the impediments to eco-theology education in Ghana were vague ecological alignment of textbooks and absence of skilled instructors. Therefore the teaching contents and methods of eco-theology based on the syllabi may fail to help address misconceptions held on by students and teachers.

Majority 57.54% of all students from both schools had the Dominion misconception while minority 41.03% of all teachers from both schools had the Dominion misconception. Averagely, majority 53.87 % of all 113 students similar to majority 53.85 % of all teachers from both schools had the Divine Intervention misconception. Majority 63.72 % of all students close the majority 61.54% of all teachers from both schools had the Divine Apocalypse Misconceptions. Averagely, majority 60.18% of all 113 students and majority 92.31% of all teachers from both schools disagreed to the Afterlife Misconception.

These empirical findings of eco-theology relate to Gottlieb's (2009) reports on the Dominion misconception; Hope & Jones' (2014) findings on the Divine Intervention misconception and the Afterlife misconception; and (Hope & Jones, 2014); and Shehu (2015) findings on the Divine Apocalypse misconception, the Fatalism and Spirituality misconception (Shehu, 2015).

CONCLUSION

The percentages of responds from all students and teachers revealing misconceptions were not convincing but these percentages could serve as a starting point for further eco-theology education since a very huge number of the participants regularly engaged in religious activities. This was in contrast to the findings of Altmeyer (2021) whose research revealed that environmental education was less feasible through religious education for the 14- to 16-year-old students at secondary schools in Germany and Austria since the number of the participants who regularly engaged in religious was not huge as compared to the participants of this study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is central that environmental proficiencies are developed in tutors to empower the greening of schools. Theoretical and practical inferences for outlining the job drill of tutors in schools must be offered (Robina-Ramírez, Sánchez-Hernández, Jiménez- and Díaz-Caro, 2020).

The concept of "We reap what we sow" promoting the concepts of environmental stewardship and accountability could be employed to correct these misconceptions. The concepts of stewardship and accountability in eco-theology education are suggested by several literature such as Altmeyer (2021) and Conradie, et. al., (2014).

Also, the religious education syllabi for basic schools in Ghana contained conspicuous contents for environmental education. These could serve as a pivot for additional eco-theology education. However, the roles of God and man in environmental protection must be clarified as the religious education syllabi for basic schools could not.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Altmeyer, S. (2021). Religious education for ecological sustainability: an initial reality checks using the example of everyday decision-making. *Journal of Religious Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40839-020-00131-5>. 69:57–74.

Asare, J. K. (2022). Eco-Theology: Content Analysis Of The Teaching Contents Employed For Environmental Education In The Religious Education Curricula From Basic Schools To High Schools In Ghana. *Science Open*. Doi: 0.14293/S2199-1006.1.SOR-PP5DV64.v 1

Awuah-Nyamekye (2019). The role of religious education in Environmental conservation in Ghana. *Crossing the Border: International Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*. 7 (1).

Boersema, J., Blowers, A. & Martin, A. (2008). The Religion- Environment Connection, 5:4, 217-221, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield. DOI: 10.1080/15693430802542257.

Botica, A. (2013). Weather, Agriculture, and Religion in the Ancient near East and in the Old Testament. *Perichoresis*. Versita Emerging Science Publishers. Volume 11. Issue 1 (2013): 95-122

Conradie, E. M., Bergmann, S., Deane-Drummond, C. , & Edwards, D. (eds.) (2014). *Christian Faith and the Earth: Current Paths and Emerging Horizons in Ecotheology*. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc. DOI 10.2478/ perc-2013-0005

Ghana Statistical Service (2012). *The 2010 Population and Housing Census of Ghana*. Accessed on 1st October, 2022. Ghana. Accra.

Goldingay, J. (2006). *Old Testament Theology: Israel's Faith*. Vol. 2. Downers Grove, IL.

Gottlieb, R. S. (2009). Religion and the environment. Chapter 29. 17, 215, 231.

Gregersen, N. H. & Mogensen, M. (Eds.). (2009). *Fra skabelsesteologitildybdeinkarnation. Om klimaforandringens ø kologiogetologi, in Klimakrisen – hvadvedvi, hvadtror vi, oghvadg ø r vi?* 14– 40. Ny Mission, 16. Frederiksberg: Unitas.

Hope, A. L.B. & Jones C.R. (2014). The impact of religious faith on attitudes to environmental issues and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies: A mixed methods study. *Elsevier. Technology in Society*, 38, 48–59. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/etd/1529>.

Hynd, C. (2001). Refutational texts and the change process. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 35, 699-714. Intervarsity Press.

Kim, G. & Han, J.-S. (2013). *Colonialism and the Transformative Spirit*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

King, S. J. (2013). *Overcoming Misconceptions in Religious Education: The Effects of Text Structure and Topic Interest on Conceptual Change*. All Graduate Theses and Dissertations.

Posner, G., Strike, K. Hewson, P. & Gertzog, W. (1982). Accommodation of a science conception: toward a theory of conceptual change. *Science Education*, 66, 2, 211–227.

Reif, F. (1987). Instructional design, cognition and technology: applications to the teaching of science concepts, *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 24, 4, 309–324.

Robina-Ramírez, R., Sánchez-Hernández, M.I., Jiménez-Naranjo, H.V., and Díaz-Caro, C. (2021). The Challenge of Greening Religious Schools by Improving the

Environmental Competencies of Teachers. *Frontiers in Psychology*. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00520.

Schuman, S., Dokken, J-V., Van Niekerk, D. & Loubser, R.A., 2018. 'Religious beliefs and climate change adaptation: A study of three rural South African communities', *Jàmbá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies* 10(1), a509. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v10i1>.

Shehu, M. U. (2015). Religion and the Environment in Northeast Nigeria: Dominion, Stewardship, Fatalism and Agency. A thesis submitted for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

Unstad, L. & Fjørtoft, H. (2021). Texts, readers, and positions: Developing a Conceptual Tool for Teaching Disciplinary Reading in Religious Education. *Learning and Instruction Journal*. 73. 101431.

Van Hise, Y. (1988). Student misconceptions in mechanics: an international problem? *The Physics Teacher*, November, 1988, 498–502.

Villa-Vicencio, C. (1999/2000). Christianity and Human Rights. *Journal of Law and Religion*. 14(2). 579– 600.

Webb, C. (2007). Deepening Conversion. 2007 CES Satellite Broadcast Salt Lake City, UT: The Church Educational System. (pp. 1-4).